

WHAT IS VENEFIT VARICOSE VEIN TREATMENT?

The circulatory system that allows the blood to travel through the body does not function well sometimes. In certain areas of the legs and feet, the valves that carry the appropriate amount of blood do not open and close properly. Due to this blood collects in certain passages and these passages start to enlarge and bulge, which causes mild discomfort or pain. When the unsightly lines developing on your legs are visible clearly then it might be time to seek [vein treatment san diego](#). There are many **varicose vein treatment** strategies that can relieve pain take care of cosmetic issues.

One therapeutic solution, among the many offered, is called Venefit. It is used to treat pain and the outward appearance of unflattering lines that start to become evident through the skin. With the Venefit system, **vein doctor san diego** inserts a catheter into the diseased area of the circulatory system to treat the area with heat. The heat causes collagen in the walls of the blood passageway to shrink, thus closing off the area and rerouting the collected blood to healthy places where the circulatory system can help blood continue its journey back to the heart.

A **varicose vein treatment san diego** like this is considered minimally invasive, and the patient will be able to walk away from the procedure without having to worry about any

serious complications. Very little pain involved with this therapy as compared to other more invasive procedures additionally. Most patients report a noticeable improvement in their symptoms within a week or two of having the procedure done.

If this **vein center san diego** option is of interest to you, schedule a consultation with a specialist at a venous care center in your area. Once this [vein specialist san diego](#) is able to go over your medical history and examine your trouble spots, he or she will be able to recommend the course of treatment that is ideal for your unique situation. If your veins are not quite to the stage of being varicose yet, the specialist may want you to try some other therapy before you resort to Venefit.

Sometimes, an exercise routine or the use of a compression stocking is enough to combat the problem. In any event, it is important to seek the guidance of a **vein specialist** who knows about the inner workings of the circulatory system before any course of action is decided upon. The more you are able to learn about your condition, the more likely you will be able to prevent these problems from recurring in the future.

What is the Cost of Venefit treatment?

VNUS procedure cost is approximate \$750b per catheter. The total cost will depend on the size of the vein treated and the total number of catheters required. On the location of the **vein doctor**, the cost will also vary. Insurance may cover at least a portion of the cost of varicose veins are accompanied by symptoms. To make the procedure affordable for patients many doctors will offer financing programs.